

A new observation of rice defoliator in Nepal

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A new pest of rice *Amata nr fortunei* Del'orza of the family Amatidae was observed Aug-Sep 1985 in the field and in the greenhouse at KAS. Infestation was much more severe in the greenhouse.

Both sexes are small black moths with yellow markings (see figure). The adult male is 1 cm long with black, feathery antennae; the female is 1.1 to 1.2 cm long with straight antennae.

Larvae are black with white hairs. Maximum length of the full-grown larva is 1.5 cm. The larvae coil their bodies and hang in a silken thread when disturbed. They are solitary and in the early stages feed on chlorophyll of the

Larva (a) and adults (b) of *Amata nr fortunei*, family Amatidae, found in Nepal.

rice leaves in parallel lines, giving the impression of hispa or leptispa damage. In later instars, the larvae feed on all the leaf but the midrib. Overall damage is similar to that of armyworm.

Pupation takes place within a papery cocoon at the base of the rice plant or on any nearby object. The moth emerges

in 14-17 d. The female lays its egg in the morning in nonoverlapping chains. Eggs are oval and creamy white. They were observed on both surfaces of rice leaves as well as on other objects.

Specimens were identified by A. T. Barrion, Entomology Department, IRRI. □

Effect of silicate materials on rice crop pests

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We assessed the effect of sodium metasilicate (48.5% SiO₂), furnace slag (20.2% SiO₂), and rice husk (14.5% SiO₂) at 1 t SiO₂/ha on incidence of rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall), rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason, and leaf folder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guen.

Experimental soil was sandy clay

loam with pH 7.0, EC 0.25 dS/m, 0.72% organic C, and 55.4 ppm available Si (N.NaOHC, pH 4.0).

Rice husk, furnace slag, and sodium metasilicate significantly reduced the thrips population (see table). Although silicate materials did not have much influence on GM incidence at tillering, a significant decrease was observed at panicle initiation. The addition of silicate materials also reduced LF incidence during panicle initiation.

Rice husk was superior to furnace slag and sodium metasilicate in reducing LF incidence. □

Effect of silicate materials on incidence of rice pests. Tamil Nadu, India, 1985.

Treatment	Tillering		Panicle initiation	
	Thrips (no./leaf)	Gall midge (%)	Gall midge (%)	Leaf folder (%)
Control	10	11.3	24.7	28.0
Sodium metasilicate	6	9.8	23.1	21.8
Furnace slag	6	10.7	18.2	18.7
Rice husk	7	10.0	20.4	18.0
LSD (0.05)	1	ns	2.2	2.3

A rearing technique for *Conocephalus longipennis* (de Haan) (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae)

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The grasshopper *C. longipennis* common in ricefields is considered a predator, but it has been shown to attack rice, especially developing grains. It has also been observed to feed on rice foliage and flowers.

As a predator, it attacks the eggs of

rice bugs, stem borers, and leaf folders and the nymphs and adults of hoppers, leaf folders, and whorl maggots.

To study its status as a predator or as a pest, a rearing method was needed.

Field-collected adult *C. longipennis* were confined on 45-d-old TN1 rice plants (see figure). Leaf sheaths bearing eggs were cut from rice plants and transferred to petri dishes lined with moist filter paper. Newly emerged first instars were transferred individually (to prevent cannibalism) to 15.0-cm test tubes (1.6 cm in diameter) and provided with southwestern corn borer diet.